

Double star detection1. Introduction

This chapter summarises some results of a preliminary study on expected astrometric effects of parasitic stars ('parasites'), i.e. unwanted stars in the IFOV bright enough to endanger the positional accuracy aimed at for the program stars. Putting the limit of acceptable disturbances at $0''.002$ it is found that at least 20 % of the program stars are accompanied by potentially dangerous parasites. In 90 % of the cases the parasite turns out to be a physical companion to the program star; thus, our discussion is focused on double and multiple stars although many results are directly applicable also to the remaining 10 % cases when the parasite is a field star in either FOV.

Statistical considerations of this kind demonstrate that an important part of the optimisation criterion must be the ability of instrument and software to detect parasites and eliminate their influence on measurements. This has, in particular, great impact on the design of the grid.

In this chapter we shall, however, for illustration and easy numerical interpretation, always assume that observations are made with a specific instrument (the 'baseline instrument'), provisionally optimised for double-star detection. This comprises an aberration-free telescope with two $160 \times 80 \text{ mm}^2$ apertures (linear obstruction factor 0.5) and a (locally) monodimensional rectangular grid with period $s = 1''.4$ and slit width $r = 0''.33$. The effective wavelength is 425 nm . The IFOV is circular with diameter $30''$. As a typical observation we may consider a 4^{S} record of a 9^{m} star (single, double, or multiple), comprising about 3000 counts with negligible background. Assuming photon noise to be the dominant error source at this intensity level, we find that the one-coordinate accuracy of one single-star observation is $0''.006$. For the entire 2.5 year mission we aim at a mean error of $0''.002$ for positions, proper motions, and parallaxes.

2. Statistics of parasitic stars

With our baseline instrument the maximum displacement of the measured position of a program star caused by another star Δm magnitudes fainter

is of the order of $0.2 \text{ dex}(-0.4 \Delta m)$, cf. Fig. 2. As a practical rule we may therefore regard all stars with $\Delta m < 5$ as parasites.

2.1. Accidental field stars

The solid angle on the sky of the two projections of the IFOV is 10^{-4} deg^2 . Taking averages over the whole sky we then expect the following number of accidental field stars in the IFOV brighter than blue magnitude m (Allen 1973, p.243):

m	6	8	10	12	14
$N(m)$	$7.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$

For a ninth magnitude program star the chance of getting a parasitical field star is 0.02.

2.2. Double and multiple stars

The statistical properties of double and multiple stars have been studied and summarised by Heintz (1969), from which the distributions given below have been derived. In the following, the term 'system' denotes a single, double, or multiple star.

The fractions of systems with 1, 2, 3, 4, ... components are, respectively, 0.30, 0.47, 0.15, 0.05, ... For double stars the joint distribution of separations (ρ) and visual magnitude differences (Δm) can be written

$$\text{Pr} [\rho < R \text{ and } \Delta m < h] = [1 + (R/R_0)^{-0.7}]^{-0.5} [1 - (1 - h/13)^2],$$

$$0 \leq h \leq 13 \quad (1)$$

where R_0 is 4.8 times the median separation, or $R_0 = 1.5, 0.9, \text{ and } 0.5$ for primary blue magnitudes $m_1 = 5, 7, 9$. (It will be assumed that the distribution (1) holds also for blue magnitude differences Δm .) Eq. (1) shows that the secondary will be parasitical for nearly 60 % of the double stars. However, systems with $\rho < 0.25$ will be observed by their photocentres and are less harmful; thus 21 % of the double stars have 'dangerous' parasites ($0.25 < \rho < 15''$ and $\Delta m < 5$).

The distributions of ρ and Δm for multiple systems are not so well known. Assuming, rather arbitrarily, that each of the $n-1$ companions in an

$R_0 \approx 6''^{-0.12 B}$

n-fold system may, with probability 0.21, be a dangerous parasite to the primary, we obtain the following distribution of the number of dangerous parasites for all systems:

number of dangerous parasites	0	1	2	≥ 3
fraction of systems	0.800	0.181	0.017	0.002

The cases with two or more dangerous parasites are essentially neglected in the subsequent discussion. Most of these cases are surely detected by the tests designed to detect one parasite, and it seems likely that part of the perturbations can be removed by applying correction methods developed for the one-parasite case.

3. Effects of an undetected parasite

3.1. Positional bias and scatter of residuals

For the purpose of this study we characterise a double star by the four parameters m_1 = blue magnitude of primary, Δm = magnitude difference (≥ 0), ρ = separation in arcsec, and θ = position angle of secondary. For the moment, these are supposed to be constant throughout the mission. The position of the primary is desired.

Fig. 1 indicates the scanning geometry. The apparent direction of scan ψ is perpendicular to the slits in this part of the grid. Disregarding measurement noise, the position of the slit at the derived moment of transit is displaced a distance b from the primary (bias). The bias is a function of Δm and the projected separation $d = \rho \cos(\psi - \theta)$. With a periodic grid $b(\Delta m, d)$ is periodic in d as illustrated in Fig. 2.

A two-coordinate position of the system is eventually obtained by combining several scans in different directions. The image not being radially symmetric, the different scans (if more than two) generally do not define a unique position, even in absence of noise. The least squares position is

$$x_0 = \frac{\langle b[\Delta m, \rho \cos(\psi_i - \theta)] \cos \psi_i \rangle}{\langle \cos^2 \psi_i \rangle}, \quad y_0 = \frac{\langle b[\Delta m, \rho \cos(\psi_i - \theta)] \sin \psi_i \rangle}{\langle \sin^2 \psi_i \rangle} \quad (2)$$

and the mean square residual

$$\epsilon^2 = \langle b[\Delta m, \rho \cos(\psi_i - \theta)]^2 \rangle - \frac{1}{2}(x_o^2 + y_o^2) \quad (3)$$

When measurement noise is included (x_o, y_o) becomes the two-dimensional positional bias and ϵ^2 the increase in residual scatter due to model mismatch.

The actual quantities x_o, y_o, ϵ depend on the distribution of ψ_i , which depends on the type of grid, the mode of scanning the sky, and the celestial position of the double star. Assuming for simplicity a uniform distribution of ψ_i on $[0, 2\pi[$ and putting $\theta = 0$, we find $y_o = 0$ and x_o, ϵ depending on Δm and ρ as shown in Fig. 3. Clearly, the effects of the parasite are completely different for unresolved and resolved systems:

- /1/ for $\rho < 0''.25$, $\epsilon = 0$ and $x_o = \rho[1 + \text{dex}(0.4\Delta m)]^{-1}$;
- /2/ for $\rho > 0''.5$, $\epsilon \approx 0''.1 \text{dex}(-0.4\Delta m)$ and x_o is oscillating between $\pm 0''.1 \text{dex}(-0.4\Delta m)$.

Thus, the photocentre, which is what in effect is observed for an unresolved system, is completely without significance for a resolved system.

3.2. Unresolved double stars: effects on proper motions and parallaxes

To get the accurate proper motion and parallax of a double star one should ideally observe the centre of gravity of the system. The actually observed photocentre (for close systems) does not, in general, coincide with the centre of gravity but describes an ellipse around it with apparent semi-major axis

$$p = a \left| \frac{1}{1 + \text{dex}(0.4\Delta m)} - \frac{M_2}{M_1 + M_2} \right| \quad (4)$$

where a is the semi-major axis of the apparent orbit and M_1, M_2 are the masses of the components. To study the effects on proper motion and parallax of the motion of the photocentre we shall assume that the true orbit is circular. Thus, the relative motion of the photocentre is

$$\xi(t) = p \cos(nt + \phi), \quad \eta(t) = p \cos i \sin(nt + \phi) \quad (5)$$

where ξ is measured along the major axis, ϕ is an orbital phase angle and i is the inclination of the orbit to the plane of the sky. The mean motion n (rad yr^{-1}) is given by Kepler's third law

$$n = 2\pi (\bar{\omega}/a)^{3/2} (M_1 + M_2)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

in which $\bar{\omega}$ is the parallax.

Proper motions

The mean square apparent velocity of the photocentre relative to the centre of gravity is, averaging over time and inclinations,

$$\langle \dot{\xi}^2 + \dot{\eta}^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2} p^2 n^2 \langle 1 + \cos^2 i \rangle = \frac{2}{3} p^2 n^2 \quad (7)$$

If the interval of observation ($T = 2.5$ yr) is short compared with the orbital period $P = 2\pi/n$, then the rms expected error in either proper motion component is $pn/\sqrt{3}$. Taking into account the finite T we obtain, by assuming uniform distribution of observations over T ,

$$\mu_{\text{rms}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} p n \left| \frac{\sin(nT/2) - (nT/2) \cos(nT/2)}{(nT/2)^3} \right| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} p n \left| 1 - \frac{1}{10}(nT/2)^2 + \dots \right| \quad (8)$$

By means of the double-star statistics given in Section 2 (with the statistical relation $\rho = 0.8 a$), the relation between masses and absolute blue magnitudes (Allen 1973, p. 209; both stars are supposed to be main sequence stars), and the distribution of parallaxes for stars of a given apparent magnitude, we can derive the distribution of μ_{rms} for systems of a given magnitude. Table 1 gives the results for $m_1 = 7$ and 9.

Table 1. Fraction of systems of apparent magnitude m_1 for which $\mu_{\text{rms}} > u$. μ_{rms} is the expected error in the proper motion components caused by the orbital motion of the photocentre of an unresolved non-single star.

u (arcsec/yr)	$m_1 = 7$	$m_1 = 9$
0.0005	0.22	0.26
0.001	0.19	0.16
0.002	0.11	0.09
0.003	0.08	0.03
0.005	0.05	0.02
0.01	0.006	0.002
0.02	0.002	0.0003

The numbers in Table 1 actually underestimate the number of systems with significant proper motion error of this kind, firstly, because we have neglected orbital eccentricities (the average e is 0.5), secondly, because μ_{rms} in (8) is already an averaged quantity (over ϕ and i), and thirdly, because we have supposed all stars to be of luminosity type V, thus neglecting e.g. systems including a white dwarf, in which case the p/a ratio is often much higher.

Clearly, the effects of unresolved systems on proper motions are not negligible, although not very alarming either. To take a positive point of view, we may say that the satellite will probably detect a significant number of new astrometric double stars (e.g. by comparing proper motions with ground-based data).

Parallaxes

With similar assumptions, the following formula may be derived for the rms relative parallax error:

$$\tilde{\omega}_{rms} / \tilde{\omega} = \sqrt{(5/21)} p \left| \frac{\sin[(n-2\pi)T/2]}{(n-2\pi)T/2} - \frac{\sin(nT/2)}{nT/2} \frac{\sin(\pi T)}{\pi T} \right| \quad (9)$$

As expected this mechanism shows a strong resonance near $P = 1$, the peak becoming narrower the longer the observing interval T . The maximum relative rms error is about 20 % (for $P = 1$ and $\Delta m = 3$); it is greater than 10 % only for $0.9 < P < 1.25$ yr and $1 < \Delta m < 8$, which will be the case for about 1 % of all systems. Although this is probably an underestimate for the same reasons as for the proper motion effect, it appears that the parallax effect is, statistically, negligible.

4. Detection of dangerous parasites

Turning now to what we have called the dangerous parasites, i.e. those with $0''.25 < \rho < 15''$ and $\Delta m < 5$, we must look for methods to detect them and as far as possible eliminate their detrimental effects. One can envisage at least three largely independent ways of doing this, working at different levels:

- /1/ a priori detection (to be considered already when setting up the observing program);
- /2/ light-curve analysis (real-time or almost-real-time processing);
- /3/ analysis of residuals (for the final reductions).

Being to some extent complementary, the three methods should of course be working in parallel.

4.1. A priori detection

This means that the program star is beforehand known to be double or multiple. In such cases we generally have some additional information, e.g. approximate values for ρ , θ , and Δm ; in the very best cases a 'definitive' orbit is available. In spite of several newly developed techniques for observation of double stars (for a review see, e.g., Franz 1973), photoelectric area-scanning in particular, the bulk of visual double star data is still the result of some 150 years of visual micrometer measures.

The Index Catalogue of Visual Double Stars (IDS; Jeffers et al. 1963) lists all measured visual double stars up to 1961.0; the version on punched cards is continuously kept up to date. From the completeness factors given by Heintz (1969) and his Table I we find that IDS should contain about 70 % of the systems of magnitude $m_1 = 8 - 9$ with $0''.25 < \rho < 15''$ and $\Delta m < 5$, at least for $\delta > -30^\circ$. The value of a priori information on Δm and d for the determination of the position of a program star was estimated by adding the inverted a priori covariance matrix to the information matrix associated with the five parameters involved in the two-star problem (Section 4.2). Some results for $\Delta m = 3$ are shown in Fig. 4. The figure gives the positional mean error (σ_1) of the program star (4^S observation, $m_1=9$) as function of projected distance to the parasite (d), for a few different combinations of a priori mean errors Σ_d and $\Sigma_{\Delta m}$. It clearly demonstrates the usefulness of even very moderately accurate prior information. In view of the very slow changes of ρ and θ for the majority of double stars (for $m_1 = 9$ and $\rho = 1$ the median relative motion of the secondary is $0''.002 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) it seems quite realistic to assume $\Sigma_d = 0''.1 - 0''.2$ for a substantial fraction of systems. The magnitudes given by IDS are visual; allowing for uncertainties of statistical transformations to blue magnitudes $\Sigma_{\Delta m} = 0.5$ may be reasonable.

4.2. Light-curve analysis

This is the analysis of an observation (count record) in terms of one or several superposed elementary light curves, each of which represents the response for a single star in the IFOV. In this context the detection problem may be regarded as a multiple-hypothesis test: if H_n is the hypothesis that there are exactly n stars in the IFOV (program stars and dangerous parasites), then $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_{n_{\max}}$ are sequentially tested against each other and the hypothesis with smallest n giving satisfactory

fit is accepted.

In H_n the observation may be modeled as an inhomogeneous Poisson process with intensity

$$I_n(t) = B + \sum_{j=1}^n \text{dex}(-0.4 m_j) i(t - t_j), \quad m_1 \leq m_2 \leq \dots \leq m_n, \quad n \leq n_{\max} \quad (10)$$

where $i(t)$ is the elementary light curve, supposed to be accurately known from theory or observations of bright single stars. There are $2n + 1$ parameters, *viz.* m_j , t_j , the magnitude and transit time of the j :th brightest star, and B = background intensity. Thus, application of H_n amounts to estimating the $2n + 1$ parameters by fitting I_n to the count record, and computing a goodness-of-fit measure.

The maximum number of parameters giving distinguishable light curves equals the number of independent Fourier components of the elementary light curve. For a periodic grid the latter is limited by diffraction. If A is the maximum linear dimension of the aperture in a direction normal to the slits, we must therefore have

$$n_{\max} \leq \text{entier}(sA/\lambda_{\min}), \quad (11)$$

s being the grid period in radians and $\lambda_{\min}$ the short wavelength cut-off. From the point of view of multiple star detection by light curve analysis one would therefore like to have s as big as possible; however, the single-star mean error increases with s so that a compromise must be found. Because cases with $n \geq 3$ are comparatively rare (2 %) and we do have other means of detection, there seems to be little point in having $n_{\max} > 2$. For $A = 160$ mm and $\lambda_{\min} = 350$ nm, as for the baseline instrument, $n_{\max} = 3$ is possible for $s > 1''.35$; however, our choice of $s = 1''.4$ optimises the instrument for $n = 2$ and gives very poor resolution for $n = 3$.

Having established a parametrised stochastic observation model and chosen a suitable test statistic (e.g. the likelihood ratio), one can now compute the probabilities of detection (accepting H_2 when this is true) and false alarm (accepting H_2 when H_1 is true) as functions of the true parameters, observing time, and acceptance criterion. With an acceptance criterion such that the probability of false alarm is 0.01 we obtain the results given in Fig. 5 and Table 2.

Table 2. Situations when the parasite is 'just detectable', i.e. probability of detection = 0.5, probability of false alarm = 0.01. The data given depends only on the total number of counts and are valid for $m_1 = 9$ and $\tau = 20^S$, or $m_1 = 8$ and $\tau = 8^S$, etc., where τ is the accumulated observing time on the system with nearly the same ψ .

Δm	minimum distance from primary $d_{\min}$	positional bias of primary $b(\Delta m, d_{\min})$
0	0"09	0"045
1	0.11	0.031
2	0.16	0.020
3	0.26	0.010
>3.5	(no detection)	< 0.007

For unresolved systems ($\rho < 0"25$) detection is indeed possible in favorable position angles, but is generally not desired. For $\rho > 0"25$ it is rather unlikely that a parasite with $\Delta m < 3$ remains undetected after the system have been scanned in several different directions (ψ_1). The difficult cases are then parasites with $3 < \Delta m < 5$, which are bright enough to create disturbances but too faint to be detected by light-curve analysis.

4.3. Analysis of residuals

It was shown in Section 3.1 that the solution for the position of a resolved system (or rather $\rho > 0"5$), obtained assuming no parasite, is expected to give an increase by ϵ^2 in the variance of residuals, where $\epsilon = 0"1 \text{ dex}(-0.4 \Delta m)$. Such a parasite should be possible to detect by a simple analysis of the residual variance, provided $\epsilon \geq \sigma_1$, the one-coordinate error for the program star. Taking $\sigma_1 = 0"006$ this condition is met for $\Delta m > 3$. Thus limitations are about the same as for the light-curve analysis method.

5. Conclusions

Stellar counts and statistics of double stars indicate that about 20 % of the observed systems (single, double, or multiple stars) are significantly ($> 0''.002$) disturbed by unwanted stars in the IFOV ('parasites'). By regular application of various tests on the observations (e.g. light-curve analysis, residual variance analysis) it will be possible, in the course of reductions, to detect and largely eliminate the effect of practically all parasites not more than three magnitudes fainter than the program star ($\Delta m < 3$). For the remaining 7 % of the systems with $3 < \Delta m < 5$ these tests are likely to fail but for at least half of them there is some a priori information (from double star catalogues) that will be useful. For the worst case of an undetected $\Delta m = 3$ parasite the disturbance on a single scan is $0''.007$ but average undetected residuals are, of course, much smaller.

Considering all this, it seems that residual systematic and accidental effects of parasites will be of the order of the final accidental mean error of a single-star position ($\sim 0''.002$) or less. Thus, although they will probably complicate the reductions considerably, parasitical stars do not seriously threaten the astrometric capabilities of the satellite.

References

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Fig. 1. Double-star scanning geometry: ρ = separation, θ = position angle of secondary, ψ = position angle of scan (always normal to the slit), b = bias, or displacement of slit at the expected transit time derived by assuming only one star.

Fig. 2. One-dimensional bias $b(\Delta m, d)$ as function of projected distance between the two components, $d = \rho \cos(\psi - \theta)$.

Fig. 3a. Two-dimensional bias x_0 (in the direction towards the parasite) resulting from several scans in different directions across a double star with separation ρ and magnitude difference Δm .

Fig. 3b. Deterministic part (ϵ) of the rms residual of the scans across a double star.

Fig. 4. Mean error (σ_1) of the one-dimensional program star position for a solution with two stars ($n = 2$), as a function of projected distance to parasite (d). Magnitude of program star $m_1 = 9$, observing time $\tau = 4^s$. Also shown are effects of various pieces of a priori information, expressed in terms of the a priori mean errors (Σ_d , $\Sigma_{\Delta m}$) of d and m .

Fig. 5. Minimum observing time (τ) on a double star with $m_1 = 9$ allowing detection of the parasite (probability of detection ≥ 0.5 , probability of false alarm = 0.01).